

A MECHANISM FOR IMPROVING RESPONSIBILITY TOWARDS THE ENVIRONMENT IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: The mechanism for improving responsibility for the environment among primary school students, methods and tools for its implementation, and work to improve a conscious attitude to nature and the environment are outlined.

Keywords: Nature, environmental problems, environmental education, Environmental protection, environmental education.

Environmental protection has always been considered one of the most pressing issues. In our country, both systematic work has been set to moderate the environment, and the fact that our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev declared 2025 the “Year of Environmental Protection and the “Green” Economy” can serve as a basis for this. When we say nature, we imagine the complex material existence surrounding us, consisting of air, water, soil, rocks, plants and animals. It is the only source that satisfies all the material and spiritual needs of a person. In this regard, she is not called "Mother Nature" for nothing, comparing her to a mother. Even though human intelligence can now "see" distances equal to several billion light years from Earth, there is no nature or life form in the Universe known to us that is similar to the nature of planet Earth.

Nowadays, when ecological problems have become a pressing issue all over the world, it is important to promote environmental education from an early age. Providing environmental education in primary grades not only increases children's love for nature, but also helps them grow into conscious citizens. Therefore, in our country, special attention is paid to improving the ecological culture of the population, especially young people. We will continue to work on strengthening public control and training highly qualified personnel.

The “Ecological Brand” of Uzbekistan has been created, reflecting the essence of environmental protection, effective and rational use of natural resources, and liability measures applied for violations in this area. Today, environmental problems are of concern to the population of the whole world. In solving these problems, it is important to increase the responsibility of the population, especially the younger generation, towards the environment. Primary school students are one of the groups that play a key role in this process. Because it is at this age that proper environmental education for children determines the attitude of the future generation to nature.

According to scientists, environmental education plays an important role in shaping the personality and sense of responsibility of children. For example, the famous ecologist E.O. Wilson noted that a person’s connection with nature has a genetic basis and is further strengthened by interacting with the environment from childhood. Also, according to psychologists and educators, when children have direct contact with nature, their environmental awareness and moral values develop.

Practical exercises and experiments. Along with theoretical knowledge, practical exercises play an invaluable role in providing children with environmental education. The following activities can increase the effectiveness of environmental education:

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Organizing trips to nature - this helps students directly observe the environment and understand natural processes.

Planting flowers and caring for trees - students understand the importance of preserving nature through the plants they plant. In order for students to feel like nature lovers in every process, and to grow up as nature lovers, it is necessary to organize practical classes in extracurricular activities.

Proper waste sorting - to form an ecological culture, it is necessary to familiarize children with the process of waste recycling. For this, it is considered a purposeful task to always have an explanatory manual posted in places where there is a lot of movement of the population.

Cooperation with parents. Parents play a large role in the effectiveness of environmental education. By organizing family ecological projects, children help to form an ecological culture not only in their families, but also in society. For example, according to the famous ecologist scientist J. Lovelock, humanity must work together to preserve the state of the planet. From this point of view, parents should participate in environmental projects with their children, learn to sort waste, and launch small initiatives to protect nature. This is a correct idea, and the correct disposal of waste is the closest way to improving the environment.

Environmental cartoons and stories for children. Visual aids have a great influence on the formation of children's environmental awareness. Through cartoons, stories and fairy tales that explain environmental problems and their solutions, children better perceive the ideas of nature conservation. For example, cartoons on environmental topics such as "Planet of Life" and "Guardian Birds" create an understanding of environmental problems in children's minds.

Methods for forming environmental responsibility

1. Environmental education in the educational process. Introductory classes in primary school classes on topics that reflect global environmental problems. Organize using information and communication technologies to explain environmental issues to students through practical exercises.

2. Demonstrative education and experimental method

Organize trips with students to nature.

Organizing practical work such as planting flowers, caring for trees, and properly sorting waste.

3. Cooperation with parents

Organizing family environmental projects.

Increasing the environmental culture of parents through children.

4. Increasing students' interest

Organizing environmental quizzes, contests, and competitions.

Creating environmental cartoons and stories for children.

The formation of environmental responsibility in primary school students is an important factor in developing the ecological culture of the future generation. This process can be further improved through the cooperation of educational institutions, parents and society. As a result, a conscious, responsible generation will be formed that ensures ecological sustainability. The Earth is our common home, and its preservation is considered the duty of every living being, and the prosperity of every inch of it is considered a global goal.

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